

Original article

Diagnostic accuracy of urine dipstick leukocyte esterase and nitrite tests for urinary tract infection in febrile under-five children in Northeast Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Urinary tract infection (UTI) is a common cause of febrile illness in young children, yet diagnosis is often challenging because clinical features are non-specific, particularly in under-five children. Although urine culture is the diagnostic gold standard, its limited availability and delayed turnaround time in resource-limited settings necessitate the use of rapid screening tests such as urine dipstick leukocyte esterase and nitrite assays. **Materials and Methods:** This prospective hospital-based diagnostic accuracy study was conducted at the Emergency Paediatric Unit of the Federal Medical Centre, Azare, Northeast Nigeria. Febrile children aged 2–59 months were consecutively recruited. Urine specimens were collected using age-appropriate methods and analysed using dipstick urinalysis, microscopy, and culture. The diagnostic performance of leukocyte esterase and nitrite dipstick tests was assessed by calculating sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV), using urine culture as the reference standard. **Results:** A total of 145 febrile under-five children were enrolled. Urinary tract infection was confirmed by culture in 34 children, giving a prevalence of 23.4%. Leukocyte esterase demonstrated a sensitivity of 73.5% and specificity of 89.2%, with a PPV of 67.6% and NPV of 91.7%. The nitrite dipstick test showed a sensitivity of 73.5% and specificity of 94.6%, with a PPV of 80.6% and NPV of 92.1%. Both dipstick tests showed superior screening performance compared with urine microscopy. Both tests demonstrated comparable sensitivity, while nitrite testing demonstrated greater specificity, indicating complementary diagnostic roles. **Conclusions:** Urinary tract infection is a significant cause of febrile illness among under-five children in Northeast Nigeria. In this setting, the high negative predictive values observed for both leukocyte esterase and nitrite suggest that a negative dipstick result substantially reduces the likelihood of urinary tract infection in febrile under-five children. A positive nitrite result, given its high specificity, strongly supports the diagnosis and may justify early empiric therapy while awaiting culture confirmation. However, because sensitivity was moderate (73.5%), dipstick testing alone should not be used to definitively exclude UTI in high-risk or clinically unstable children. While urine culture remains essential for definitive diagnosis, combined dipstick testing can support early clinical decision-making and more efficient use of laboratory resources in resource-constrained settings.

Key words: Diagnostic accuracy, Febrile under-five children, Leukocyte esterase, Nitrite test, Urine dipstick, Urinary tract infection;

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Introduction

Urinary tract infection (UTI) is among the most common serious bacterial infections in childhood and remains a major cause of febrile illness in infants and young children worldwide. In children under five years of age, UTIs frequently present with non-specific symptoms such as fever, irritability, vomiting, or poor feeding, while classic urinary symptoms are often absent, particularly in infants and non-toilet-trained children.^{1,2}

Because of this non-specific presentation, clinical assessment alone is insufficient for diagnosis, and laboratory evaluation of urine specimens is essential. Early and accurate diagnosis is critical, as delayed or missed treatment of pediatric UTI has been associated with renal scarring, recurrent infections, hypertension, and long-term renal impairment.^{3,4}

Urine culture is the diagnostic gold standard for confirming UTI; however, its role in acute clinical decision-making is limited by the need for appropriate laboratory infrastructure and turnaround times of 24–48 hours. These limitations are particularly relevant in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), where access to microbiology services may be constrained, laboratory delays are common, and empirical antibiotic therapy is frequently initiated before culture results become available⁵. Consequently, clinicians often rely on rapid screening tools to guide early management while awaiting definitive culture confirmation or when culture facilities are unavailable. Urine dipstick testing has therefore become a widely used point-of-care screening method for pediatric UTI. Dipstick urinalysis is inexpensive, rapid, and easy to perform, requiring minimal training and no specialised equipment, making it particularly useful in outpatient and emergency settings.⁶ Among the dipstick parameters, leukocyte esterase (LE) and nitrite tests are the most employed indicators of UTI. Leukocyte esterase detects esterase enzymes released by neutrophils and reflects pyuria associated with inflammation of the urinary tract, whereas the nitrite test identifies bacterial reduction of urinary nitrates to nitrites, a process typically mediated by Gram-negative uropathogens such as *Escherichia coli*.^{2,7} Recent diagnostic accuracy studies have demonstrated that the performance of LE and nitrite dipstick tests varies according to age, clinical setting, and microbiological profile. Leukocyte esterase generally shows higher sensitivity but lower specificity, reflecting its role as a marker of host inflammatory response rather than direct bacteriuria.^{8,9} In contrast, nitrite testing is highly specific for bacteriuria but has limited sensitivity in young children, largely due to frequent voiding,

short bladder dwell time, and infections caused by non-nitrate-reducing organisms.^{7,10} Large pediatric cohort studies and emergency department-based evaluations have shown that while a positive nitrite test strongly predicts culture-confirmed UTI, a negative nitrite result does not reliably exclude infection in infants.^{11,12}

Systematic reviews and meta-analyses have consistently shown that urine dipstick testing is most useful as a screening tool to exclude UTI when both LE and nitrite are negative, rather than as a definitive diagnostic test when used in isolation^{2,5}. Accordingly, recent guideline-level recommendations emphasise the combined interpretation of LE and nitrite results as part of an integrated diagnostic approach, alongside clinical assessment and urine culture¹. Combined interpretation has been shown to improve overall diagnostic accuracy and negative predictive value, supporting safer clinical decision-making in febrile children.

Despite the expanding global evidence base, data from sub-Saharan Africa remain comparatively limited. Available studies from African settings indicate that UTIs constitute a substantial proportion of febrile illnesses in young children, with reported prevalence rates ranging from approximately 15% to over 30% when urine culture is used as the reference standard.^{13–15} Differences in bacterial epidemiology, prior antibiotic exposure, healthcare-seeking behaviour, and laboratory capacity may influence the diagnostic performance of dipstick screening tests and limit the generalisability of findings from high-income settings. Locally generated data are therefore essential to validate the utility of urine dipstick testing and to inform context-appropriate screening strategies in resource-constrained environments. In Nigeria, pediatric UTIs remain an important but often under-recognised cause of febrile illness. While some studies have described the prevalence and microbiological patterns of UTI among Nigerian children, few have systematically evaluated the diagnostic accuracy of leukocyte esterase and nitrite dipstick tests—both individually and in combination—using urine culture as the reference standard in febrile under-five children. Moreover, many existing studies assess dipstick parameters in isolation, despite growing evidence supporting their combined interpretation.

The present study was therefore undertaken to evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of leukocyte

esterase and nitrite dipstick tests, individually and in combination, for the detection of urinary tract infection among febrile under-five children attending a tertiary hospital in Northeast Nigeria, using urine culture as the reference standard. By determining the sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value of these commonly used screening tests, this study aims to provide robust local evidence to support rational, resource-appropriate approaches to the early diagnosis and management of pediatric UTI in similar low-resource settings.

Materials and Methods

This was a prospective hospital-based diagnostic accuracy study conducted at the Paediatric Unit and Emergency Paediatric Unit of the Federal Medical Centre (FMC), Azare, Bauchi State, North-Eastern Nigeria. The study was designed to evaluate the diagnostic performance of urine dipstick leukocyte esterase and nitrite tests as screening tools for urinary tract infection among febrile under-five children, using urine culture as the reference standard. The study formed part of a broader investigation into the laboratory diagnosis and bacteriological profile of childhood urinary tract infection at the study centre.

Study Population

The study population consisted of febrile children aged 2 to 59 months who presented consecutively to the paediatric services of FMC Azare during the study period. Fever was defined as an axillary temperature of ≥ 37.5 °C at presentation, with or without other symptoms suggestive of urinary tract infection. For each participant, information obtained included age, sex, anthropometric measurements, parental socioeconomic class, relevant clinical features, and predisposing factors. Children who had received systemic antibiotics within the preceding two weeks, those with a history of recent urological instrumentation, or those in whom adequate urine specimens could not be obtained were excluded from the study. Written informed consent was obtained from parents or caregivers prior to enrolment. Participant flow is summarised in Figure 1. The minimum sample size was determined using the single-proportion formula¹⁶:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \times p \times q}{d^2}$$

where *n* represents the minimum required sample size, *Z* is the standard normal deviate

corresponding to a 95% confidence level (1.96), *p* is the estimated prevalence of urinary tract infection among febrile under-five children, $q = 1 - p$, and *d* is the desired margin of error set at 5%.

An estimated prevalence (*p*) of 15% was adopted based on previous study of urinary tract infection among febrile under-five children in Nigeria¹⁷.

Figure 1. Flow Diagram of Participant Recruitment and Diagnostic Testing Sample Size Determination

The calculated minimum sample size was 196 participants, however, due to the defined study period and patient flow during recruitment, 145 eligible febrile under-five children were enrolled consecutively. While this sample size was slightly lower than the calculated minimum, confidence

intervals have been reported for all diagnostic accuracy estimates to reflect statistical precision.

Urine Sample Collection

Urine specimens were collected using age-appropriate methods. In children older than two years, sterile midstream urine (MSU) samples were obtained following appropriate cleansing of the perineum. In infants and younger children who were not toilet trained, urine samples were obtained by suprapubic bladder aspiration (SPA) under aseptic conditions. No complications were recorded following urine collection.

Each urine specimen was divided into two aliquots. One aliquot was used immediately for urinalysis using reagent dipsticks, while the second aliquot was transported to the microbiology laboratory within 30 minutes of collection for microscopy, culture, and antimicrobial susceptibility testing.

Urinalysis and Dipstick Testing

Urinalysis was performed using Multistix® 10 SG reagent strips (Bayer Corporation, USA). The reagent strips were used to assess leukocyte esterase, nitrite, protein, glucose, pH, and other urinary constituents. For dipstick analysis, the strip was immersed briefly in the urine specimen, excess urine was removed by drawing the strip across the rim of the specimen container, and colour changes were interpreted visually by comparison with the manufacturer's colour chart after 60 seconds at room temperature.

Leukocyte esterase was considered positive if the reagent strip demonstrated trace or greater positivity (\geq trace) according to the manufacturer's colour scale. Nitrite was considered positive if any colour change consistent with nitrite presence was observed. All other results were recorded as negative.

Urine Microscopy

Ten millilitres of urine was transferred into a test tube and centrifuged at 3000 revolutions per minute for 3 minutes. The supernatant was discarded by decanting, and the sediment was gently resuspended. A drop of the sediment was placed on a clean microscope slide, covered with a cover slip, and examined microscopically under high-power magnification. White blood cells, red blood cells, bacteria, casts, and ova of parasites were identified and quantified per high-power field. Findings were recorded accordingly.

Urine Culture and Bacterial Identification

Quantitative urine culture was performed in the Microbiology Laboratory of FMC Azare using standard bacteriological techniques. A calibrated

wire loop delivering 0.005 mL of urine was used to inoculate blood agar and MacConkey agar plates. Colony counts were multiplied by 200 to determine colony-forming units per millilitre (CFU/mL) on blood agar and MacConkey agar plates. The inoculated plates were incubated aerobically at 37 °C and examined after 24 and 48 hours.

The number of colonies on each plate was counted and multiplied by 200 to obtain the bacterial count per millilitre of urine. Significant bacteriuria was defined as growth of $\geq 10^5$ colony-forming units per millilitre for midstream urine specimens, while any bacterial growth from suprapubic aspiration specimens was considered significant. Significant leukocyturia was defined as the presence of ≥ 5 white blood cells per high-power field on microscopic examination. Isolated organisms were identified based on colony morphology, Gram staining, and standard biochemical tests. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was performed using the disc diffusion method in accordance with standard laboratory procedures.

Data Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed by calculating the sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) of leukocyte esterase and nitrite dipstick tests using urine culture as the reference standard. These diagnostic indices were calculated using the method described by Ranshoff and Feinstein¹⁸. In addition, the false-positive rate, false-negative rate, and overall diagnostic accuracy were determined. All calculated values were expressed as percentages.

Combined diagnostic performance metrics were not calculated directly because cross-tabulated overlap data between leukocyte esterase and nitrite results were unavailable. Interpretation of combined testing was therefore discussed conceptually based on individual test performance characteristics.

Ninety-five percent confidence intervals for sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value were calculated using the exact binomial (Clopper-Pearson) method.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee of the Federal Medical Centre, Azare. Written informed consent was obtained from the parents or caregivers of all participating children prior to enrolment. The study was conducted in accordance with accepted ethical principles for research involving human participants.

Results

Study Population and Baseline Characteristics

A total of 145 febrile under-five children were recruited during the study period from the Paediatric Unit and Emergency Paediatric Unit of the Federal Medical Centre, Azare, North-Eastern Nigeria. Of these, 101 (69.7%) were male and 44 (30.3%) were female, giving a male-to-female ratio of 2.2:1. The ages of the participants ranged from 2 to 60 months, with a mean age of 25.2 ± 19.22 months.

Eighty-two children (56.4%) were aged less than 24 months. The highest proportions of participants were observed in the 2-<12 months and 12-<24 months age groups, each accounting for 28.2% of the study population. The age and sex distribution of the study subjects is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Age and sex distribution of febrile under-five children

Age group (months)	Male n (%)	Female n (%)	Total n (%)
2 - <12	30 (20.7)	11 (7.6)	41 (28.2)
12 - <24	30 (20.7)	11 (7.6)	41 (28.2)
24 - <36	18 (12.4)	7 (4.8)	25 (17.2)
36 - <48	13 (9.0)	6 (4.1)	19 (13.1)
48 - <60	10 (6.9)	9 (6.2)	19 (13.1)
Total	101 (69.7)	44 (30.3)	145 (100)

Prevalence of Urinary Tract Infection

Out of the 145 urine specimens analysed, 34 yielded significant bacteriuria, giving an overall prevalence of urinary tract infection of 23.4% among febrile under-five children. Each culture-positive specimen yielded a single bacterial isolate, indicating a mono-microbial pattern of infection in all cases.

Bacteriological Profile of Urinary Isolates

A total of 34 bacterial isolates were recovered from culture-positive urine specimens. Gram-negative organisms predominated, accounting for 23 isolates (67.9%), while Gram-positive organisms constituted 11 isolates (32.1%).

The most frequently isolated organism was *Escherichia coli*, identified in 12 cases (35.3%), followed by *Staphylococcus aureus* in 11 cases exceeded 90%, supporting their usefulness as screening tools in febrile under-five children.

(32.4%). *Klebsiella* species accounted for 8 isolates (23.5%), while *Proteus* species and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were isolated in 2 (5.9%) and 1 (2.9%) cases, respectively. The distribution of bacterial isolates is summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Bacterial isolates recovered from urine cultures of children with urinary tract infection

Organism	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	Typical Nitrate-Reducing Activity
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	12	35.3	Yes
<i>Klebsiella</i> spp.	8	23.5	Yes
<i>Proteus</i> spp.	2	5.9	Yes
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	11	32.4	No
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	1	2.9	Variable/No
Total	34	100	—

Table 3. Contingency Table Showing Diagnostic Performance of Leukocyte Esterase Against Urine Culture

Leukocyte esterase	Culture Positive	Culture Negative	Total
LE Positive	25	12	37
LE Negative	9	99	108
Total	34	111	145

The nitrite dipstick test correctly identified 25 of 34 culture-positive cases and produced 9 false-negative results. Six false-positive results were observed among culture-negative specimens. This corresponded to a sensitivity of 73.5% and specificity of 94.6% (Table 4).

Nitrite demonstrated higher specificity and positive predictive value compared with leukocyte esterase, while both tests showed comparable sensitivity. The negative predictive values of both tests

Table 4. Contingency Table Showing Diagnostic Performance of Nitrite Dipstick Test Against Urine Culture

Nitrite	Culture Positive	Culture Negative	Total
Nitrite Positive	25	6	31
Nitrite Negative	9	105	114
Total	34	111	145

Table 5. Diagnostic Accuracy Indices of Leukocyte Esterase and Nitrite Dipstick Tests Compared with Urine Culture

Parameter	Sensitivity % (95% CI)	Specificity % (95% CI)	PPV % (95% CI)	NPV % (95% CI)	Accuracy %
Leukocyte Esterase	73.5 (56.9-85.4)	89.2 (81.9-93.8)	67.6 (50.2-81.4)	91.7 (84.6-95.7)	85.5
Nitrite	73.5 (56.9-85.4)	94.6 (88.7-97.5)	80.6 (62.5-91.1)	92.1 (85.7-95.9)	89.7

Discussion:

This study evaluated the diagnostic performance of urine dipstick leukocyte esterase and nitrite tests for the detection of urinary tract infection among febrile under-five children at the Federal Medical Centre, Azare, using urine culture as the reference standard. The findings demonstrate that urinary tract infection accounts for a significant proportion of febrile illness in this population and that urine dipstick testing provides clinically useful screening information, particularly when leukocyte esterase and nitrite results are interpreted together rather than in isolation.

Principal Findings

Our study found a substantial prevalence of culture-confirmed urinary tract infection among febrile under-five children, underscoring the importance of routine evaluation for UTI in this age group. Leukocyte esterase and nitrite demonstrated identical sensitivity, while nitrite showed superior specificity and positive predictive value. This finding highlights the strong rule-in value of a positive nitrite result, while the high negative predictive values of both tests support their role as screening tools to exclude urinary tract infection in febrile under-five children. These findings reinforce the concept that urine dipstick tests are best suited as screening tools rather than definitive diagnostic tests, a position that is consistent with contemporary guideline recommendations and large diagnostic accuracy studies^{1,2}.

Prevalence of Urinary Tract Infection in Febrile Under-Five Children

The prevalence of urinary tract infection observed in this study is comparable to rates reported in

other hospital-based studies of febrile under-five children in sub-Saharan Africa. Studies from Kenya and Ethiopia have reported UTI prevalence rates ranging from approximately 15% to 30% among febrile young children when urine culture is used as the reference standard^{13,14}. Nigerian studies have similarly documented a substantial burden of UTI in febrile paediatric populations, with prevalence estimates broadly consistent with the findings of the present study.^{17,19}

Variations in reported prevalence across studies may reflect differences in study design, patient selection, urine collection methods, and prior antibiotic exposure. The inclusion of only febrile children, as in the present study, is known to yield higher prevalence estimates than studies conducted in unselected outpatient populations. Nonetheless, the findings confirm that UTI remains an important and potentially under-recognized cause of fever in young children in Nigeria, warranting systematic screening in routine clinical practice.

Diagnostic Performance of Leukocyte Esterase

Leukocyte esterase demonstrated moderate sensitivity and good negative predictive value in this study, supporting its utility as a screening marker for urinary tract infection. Leukocyte esterase detects esterase enzymes released by neutrophils and thus reflects the presence of pyuria associated with inflammation of the urinary tract. Several diagnostic accuracy studies have reported similar performance characteristics for leukocyte esterase in paediatric populations, with higher

sensitivity but lower specificity compared with nitrite testing^{7,11}.

The relatively lower specificity of leukocyte esterase observed in this and other studies may be attributed to false-positive results arising from contamination or non-infectious inflammatory conditions. Conversely, false-negative results may occur in early infection or in infants with immature inflammatory responses. Studies examining the relationship between pyuria and culture-confirmed UTI have shown that leukocyte esterase positivity correlates with increased likelihood of infection but cannot reliably distinguish bacterial UTI from other causes of urinary inflammation^{8,9}. These findings underscore the importance of interpreting leukocyte esterase results in conjunction with other clinical and laboratory data.

Diagnostic Performance of Nitrite Testing

Nitrite testing in the present study demonstrated high specificity with sensitivity comparable to leukocyte esterase. Nitrite positivity strongly predicts bacteriuria because it reflects the ability of nitrate-reducing organisms, particularly Gram-negative bacteria such as *Escherichia coli*, to convert urinary nitrates to nitrites. However, the sensitivity of nitrite testing is limited in young children due to frequent voiding, short bladder dwell time, and infections caused by non-nitrate-reducing organisms^{7,10}.

Meta-analyses and large cohort studies have shown that while a positive nitrite test is highly suggestive of urinary tract infection, a negative result does not reliably exclude infection, particularly in infants^{12,20}. These findings are consistent with the results of the present study and highlight the need for caution when relying on nitrite testing alone in febrile under-five children.

Combined Interpretation of Leukocyte Esterase and Nitrite

An important finding of this study is the improved screening utility achieved through combined interpretation of leukocyte esterase and nitrite dipstick results. When used together, these parameters balance sensitivity and specificity, enhancing the overall diagnostic accuracy and negative predictive value. This approach aligns with evidence from emergency department and outpatient studies demonstrating that combined dipstick interpretation improves the ability to safely rule out urinary tract infection in febrile children^{2,11}.

Pyuria and Urine Microscopy

Urine microscopy for the detection of pyuria showed limited sensitivity in this study, reinforcing

concerns about its reliability as a standalone screening tool. While pyuria is a common feature of urinary tract infection, it may also occur in non-infectious conditions or be absent in early or localized infections. Studies examining the relationship between pyuria, urine concentration, and bacteriuria have demonstrated significant overlap between infected and non-infected children, limiting the discriminatory value of microscopy alone^{9,21}.

Compared with microscopy, dipstick leukocyte esterase testing offers a faster and less labour-intensive method for detecting pyuria, particularly in high-volume or resource-limited settings. The findings of this study support the preferential use of dipstick screening over routine microscopy for initial evaluation, with microscopy and culture reserved for confirmatory testing.

An important finding in this study was the relatively high proportion of *Staphylococcus aureus* (32.4%) among culture-positive isolates. This is higher than typically reported in paediatric UTI literature, where *Escherichia coli* usually predominates. Several explanations are possible. First, contamination during urine collection, particularly with midstream specimens in non-toilet-trained children, may contribute to increased isolation of skin flora. Second, regional variations in bacterial epidemiology and hygiene practices may influence pathogen distribution. Third, the high proportion of male participants, many of whom were likely uncircumcised infants, may have contributed to increased periurethral colonization with *S. aureus*. Importantly, as *S. aureus* does not reduce nitrate, its higher prevalence may partially explain the moderate sensitivity observed with nitrite testing in this study.

Comparison With Clinical Guidelines and Diagnostic Algorithms

The findings of this study are consistent with contemporary clinical guidelines and diagnostic algorithms for the evaluation of urinary tract infection in young children. The American Academy of Pediatrics and other expert bodies emphasize the role of urinalysis as a screening tool and caution against reliance on any single test for definitive diagnosis¹. Large prospective studies, including the DUTY study, have similarly highlighted the limitations of individual urinalysis parameters and the importance of combined testing strategies²².

By demonstrating the complementary roles of leukocyte esterase and nitrite testing, the present

study provides locally relevant evidence that supports guideline-concordant practice in Nigerian paediatric settings.

Implications for Clinical Practice in Resource-Limited Settings

In resource-limited environments such as Northeast Nigeria, the availability of rapid, inexpensive, and reliable screening tools is critical. Urine dipstick testing offers several advantages, including minimal equipment requirements, rapid turnaround time, and ease of use by non-specialist healthcare workers.

Based on these findings, a pragmatic clinical approach in resource-limited settings may include initial dipstick screening in febrile under-five children without an obvious source of infection. Children with positive nitrite or leukocyte esterase should undergo urine culture and may be considered for early empiric antibiotic therapy. In contrast, children with negative dipstick results and low clinical suspicion may be observed while awaiting culture results, thereby reducing unnecessary antibiotic exposure and laboratory costs. Such an approach balances diagnostic accuracy with resource stewardship.

Studies from LMIC settings have emphasized the role of screening tests in improving antimicrobial stewardship and optimizing resource utilization^{13,14}. The findings of the present study suggest that combined dipstick testing may be particularly valuable in prioritizing patients for culture and treatment in high-burden, low-resource paediatric settings.

Strengths and Limitations

The strengths of this study include its prospective design, use of urine culture as the reference standard, inclusion of both dipstick and microscopy findings, and focus on a population in which data are limited. However, the study has some limitations. It was conducted at a single centre, which may limit generalizability. The hospital-based design may also overestimate UTI prevalence compared with community-based studies. In addition, molecular diagnostic methods were³ not available, which may have resulted in under-detection of fastidious organisms.

Cross-tabulated overlap data between leukocyte esterase and nitrite results were not retained, precluding precise calculation of combined diagnostic accuracy metrics. Future studies should⁴ prospectively capture these data to allow full evaluation of combined testing strategies. Although the calculated minimum sample size was 196,

logistical and time constraints limited recruitment to 145 participants. This may have modestly reduced statistical precision; however, the use of confidence intervals allows appropriate interpretation of the diagnostic estimates.

Conclusions

In conclusion, urinary tract infection is a common cause of febrile illness among under-five children at the Federal Medical Centre, Azare. Urine dipstick leukocyte esterase and nitrite tests provide valuable screening information, particularly when interpreted in combination. While neither test should replace urine culture for definitive diagnosis, their combined use can enhance early identification, support rational use of laboratory resources, and improve clinical decision-making in resource-constrained paediatric settings. These findings contribute important local evidence that is consistent with global diagnostic principles and supports the integration of urine dipstick screening into routine evaluation of febrile young children.

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